

FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMERS TO SWITCH MOBILE INTERNET SERVICE PROVIDERS IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

The Internet is one of the important innovations in the Twentieth century. According to Ngai and Wat (2002) the popularity of the Internet is rising at an impressive rate due to the amount of services it offers such as ease of creating services, the presence of a single standard, and the global reach. Telecommunication companies began to grow rapidly in the market and yet found difficulty to maintain similar customer attraction for a long period of time with the advent of the Internet. As a result, customers tend to switch Internet service providers frequently.

Internet service providers (ISPs) are the companies in the telecommunication industry that provide facilities to connect users with the Internet. Number of fixed access telephone subscriptions have decreased since 2011 while mobile telephone subscription has increased continuously since it began, according to the statistics of Telecommunication regulatory commission of Sri Lanka, (TRC, 2018). In the current emerging economy customers are not loyal to one single private telecommunications firm, their satisfaction and loyalty change over time (Akbar & Parvez, 2009; Mittal et al., 1999). This switching behavior can be described as being loyal to one service provider and switching to another service provider because of frustration or other issues. (Sathish, Kumar & Naveen, 2011).

There are many studies to prove that customers are frequently changing their mobile ISPs in the global context. (Bansal, Taylor & James, 2005; Keaveney, 1995). However, it is difficult to find studies on the user's frequency of changing the ISPs in Sri Lankan context. Therefore, the researchers have conducted a small survey to identify the importance of

mobile Internet Service Providers to their users. As a result of that survey, it helped to identify frequency of customer switching between ISPs.

Data was collected from 55 respondents including teenagers, undergraduates, work age professionals and elders in this survey, and there were 90% respondents using smart phones with the mobile connections which consisted of voice and data services, based on the survey results. Further, it was revealed that 37.8% of respondents have changed their connection twice and 20% of respondents have changed their connection more than 4 times within the last 5 years. In particular, 35% of respondents have changed their previous connection within the last 6 months and 35.6% of respondents have changed their service providers in the previous year. Notably, there were only 20% respondents who have been using their service providers continuously for last year. This evident that, customer intention to switch mobile service provider is varying in the Sri Lankan context.

In previous studies on customer switching behaviors, many factors that affect customers switching intention have been identified. (Lee, Jamie & Murphy, 2012). Among them, internet service quality (Bansal, 2005; Oghojafor, 2012), call rates (Bansal, Taylor & James, 2005; Misra, Mahajan & Mahajan, 2017; Oghojafor et al., 2012; Sathish, Kumar & Naveen, 2011), Network coverage (Bansal, Taylor & James, 2005; Misra, Mahajan & Mahajan, 2017; Sathish, Kumar & Naveen, 2011), switching cost (Ahn, Han & Lee, 2006; Bansal, Taylor & James, 2005; Keramati & Ardabili, 2011), customer status (Sharma & Sachdeva, 2017), service usage (Keramati & Ardabili, 2011), switching intention (Bansal, Taylor & James, 2005; Lee & Murphy, 2005; Saeed, Hussain & Riaz, 2011), dissatisfaction (Bansal, Taylor & James, 2005; Sharma & Sachdeva, 2017), usage cost (Sathish, Kumar & Naveen, 2011), availability of alternatives (Oghojafor et al., 2012), brand image (Misra, Mahajan & Mahajan, 2017) and trust (Sarma & Sachdeva, 2017) were prominent. However, identification of factors influencing customers to switch mobile Internet Service Providers

in Sri Lankan context is worth researching for many stakeholders of the industry.

Though Internet Service Providers (ISPs) continuously cater their customer needs, customer satisfaction and loyalty on ISPs tend to decrease with time (Spiller, Vlastic & Yetton, 2007; Thaichon & Quach, 2015). This behavior of customers creates uncertainty among companies as they know that attracting new customers is more costly and less profitable than retaining existing customers (Thaichon & Quach, 2015). Decrease in loyalty and higher customer churn rate are inherent features of the telecommunication industry according to the Marketline (2014). When compared to other industries, managing customer churn in IT-based industries is reported to be difficult (Spiller et al., 2007). Organizations that manage to retain customers for a long time and control the customer churn have confirmed higher revenue and profit margins (Thaichon & Quach, 2015). Thaichon and Quach (2015) argued that overall service quality of ISP creates a favorable feeling in the mind of customers and that in turn gives them a perception of trust about the company. However, a pre-survey done by the researchers made it evident that there is no such kind of trust in customers' mind towards the mobile ISPs in Sri Lankan context.

Though many factors were identified which result customers to switch ISPs in previous literature, quality (Bansal 2005; Oghojafor, 2012; Sathish, Kumar & Naveen, 2011) of the findings are contradictory, and less attention has been given to identify factors influencing Sri Lankan customers to switch mobile internet service providers. This research study fills that gap by determining the factors that influence customers to switch between different mobile Internet Service providers (ISPs) and identifying the relationship between identified factors and customer switching intention.

It is important that organizations detect the factors of customer switching in order to keep the customers' relationship and change and execute necessary strategies with this phenomenon. This study will help organizations to identify affecting factors and make strategic plans in order to keep customer loyalty for a long time.

Methodology

A conceptual model developed based on Bansal and Tylor (1999) Service Provider Switching Model (SPSM) was used for this study (Figure 1). Five most frequently identified factors were used as independent variables of the conceptual model considering the previous research findings.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model derived from Bansal and Tylor (1999)

In order to meet the research objectives five research hypotheses were formulated. The study was conducted as a quantitative research using a cross-sectional questionnaire survey with the support of self-administered online questionnaire. The study focused on Sri Lankans who obtain the services from mobile Internet Service providers (ISPs). For the purpose of identifying the representative sample, undergraduates from University of Sri Jayewardenepura were selected using the convenience random sampling technique. This selection was done based on the belief that the undergraduates of a university would represent all the parts of the country and belong to the category of highest Internet service users in the society. Prospected survey respondents were contacted through an invitation email explaining the purpose of the survey and URL that linked to the questionnaire developed using google forms. Sample size was calculated

using ex-ante power analysis, thus the responses from 110 respondents were identified as statistically significant sample.

Based on the study objectives the data analysis was performed using regression model technique with Smart PLS software. Initially, the data were analyzed descriptively to explain the context and the perceptions of the participants. Next the model testing was done after checking the reliability and the validity of the collected data.

Results and Discussion

Majority of the respondents (68%) belong to the age category between 18 and 25 from the respondents 55% (n=61) were males. The most popular ISP among the respondents was Mobitel, while Dialog, Hutch, Airtel, and Etisalat ISPs were the service provider of respondents in various percentages (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Current internet service provider of the respondents

The time duration of using the current service provider varied among the respondents. More than half of the sample (56%) have been using their service provider for more than one year, while 19% of respondents have

been using for less than 6 months. Only 16% of respondents were using their current service provider for less than 3 months.

The reliability and the validity of the constructs was evaluated prior to the model testing. The composite reliability above the 0.7 threshold value indicated the constructs produce similar results under consistent condition (Hair et al., 2014). The convergent validity of the constructs measured through average variance extracted (AVE) above the 0.5 threshold value indicated the convergence of the items that measure each of the constructs in the model (Hair et al., 2014). Further, the discriminant validity of the constructs was also confirmed as the square root of the AVE of each construct was larger than the latent variable correlation of the constructs. Validity analysis also confirmed that the variables used in the research are acceptable as it is without any modifications.

Multiple regression analysis with SmartPLS resulted in outer loading values less than 0.7 with few questionnaire items. Thus the model was re-evaluated after eliminating those question items. The hypotheses test result were exhibited in Table 1.

Table 1. Significance testing result of the Conceptual Model

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	t-Statistics	Result
H1	Higher the Internet Service Quality of ISP, lower the switching intention of Customer	0.178	3.306 ***	Accepted
H2	Higher the Switching cost, lower the switching intention of customer	1.579	0.164	Rejected
H3	Higher the call rates, lower the switching intention of customer	0.096	1.673	Rejected
H4	Higher the trust on ISP, Lower the	3.907	3.39 ***	Accepted

	switching intention of customer			
	Higher the attractiveness of alternatives, higher the switching intention of customer			
H5		3.391	0.095	Rejected

Note: *** p<0.001, ** p<0.01

In multiple regression analysis, the predictive power of a particular model is assessed using the R-squared (R^2) values of the dependent variable. The R^2 indicates the amount of variance explained by the independent variable. It represents the quality of the model variables (Hair et al., 2010). The model resulted in an R^2 of 0.566, which resulted in a good level of predictability.

Conclusion

Only two hypotheses were supported in the model based on the hypotheses testing result. It suggested that the high Internet service quality will lower the switching intention of ISP Customers From the first supported hypothesis. The second hypothesis supported revealed that higher trust would decrease the Switching Intention of ISP customers. The study resulted in no statistically significant result on the relationship between switching cost, call rates, alternative attractiveness customers switching intention. The study would have resulted in different findings if it considered fixed ISP in addition to the mobile ISPs in Sri Lanka. The predictability of the model would have increased if the model considered variables such as network coverage, customer status, usage cost, and brand image. However, the findings from this study are believed to be important for current ISPs in Sri Lanka.

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